

Module-Level Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy analysis for SOH monitoring of Lithium-ion Batteries

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Abstract—Lithium-ion batteries play a central role in energy storage for electric vehicles and renewable energy systems. Due to their high cost and sensitivity, an efficient monitoring of their state of health is required in most applications. A typical state of health monitoring is based on capacity measurement, which takes several hours and offers only limited diagnostic insight. This contribution proposes the use of electrochemical impedance spectroscopy as a faster, non-invasive alternative capable of capturing internal degradation phenomena with better detail. Although existing research focuses mainly on individual cells, practical applications require module-level diagnostics without disassembly. This study evaluates the correlation between the state of health and equivalent electrical circuit parameters derived from electrochemical impedance spectroscopy measurements on 2P3S battery modules aged from 100% to 60% state of health. Results show that R_s , R_1 , and N_1 exhibit a strong correlation with the state of health, making them suitable for module-level diagnostics. The findings provide a foundation for developing reliable module-sorting strategies, for example at the transition between first-life and second-life applications.

Keywords—lithium-ion battery, battery module, battery ageing, battery diagnostics, electrochemical impedance spectroscopy, equivalent electrical circuit

I. INTRODUCTION

Lithium-ion battery cells are widely used in modern energy storage solutions, both in the electrified transportation sector and in systems integrating renewable energy sources [1]. At the same time, the battery remains one of the most expensive components in battery energy storage systems and electric vehicles [2]. Therefore, ensuring their stable and economically efficient use and integration is essential.

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One of the commonly used parameters for describing the condition of a battery is the state of health (SOH) [3]. The SOH parameter is defined as:

$$SOH = \frac{C_c}{C_{BOL}} * 100\% \quad (1)$$

where C_c is the capacity of the cell at specific moment in time and C_{BOL} represents the capacity of the cell at the beginning of life. This formula can be applied not only to individual cells, but also to battery modules and battery packs [4]. The standard approach for determining the SOH of a battery cell is reference performance testing (RPT) [5] based on capacity measurements [2]. Although this method is one of the most straightforward to implement, it provides limited insight into the overall condition of the cells [2] and is relatively time-consuming, typically requiring several hours [5] to days [6] to complete. As a result, researchers have sought to develop faster methods for battery testing.

One potential solution is the use of electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) [7]. This method is based on exciting the tested battery cell with a low-amplitude sinusoidal while recording the corresponding response. By comparing the input and output signals, an EIS curve representing the impedance as a function of frequency is obtained, mostly visualized as a Nyquist diagram [8]. Each region of this curve is associated with a different electrochemical process, such as an increase in internal resistance, growth of the solid electrolyte interphase (SEI) layer, or changes in the charge transfer region [9].

These characteristics, along with the significantly shorter measurement time (ranging from minutes to even seconds [7]) have led to increased interest in this method and to experimental efforts focused on extracting SOH-related information from the EIS curve.

Pang et al. [10] proposed a method based on the ratio between the real part of the zero-crossing of the Nyquist plot and the real part of its low-frequency inflection point. Li et al. [11] utilized EIS-measured curves to estimate SOH using a

transfer learning-based deep neural network model. Sihvo et al. [12], report that individual parameters extracted from fitting EIS to an equivalent electrical circuit (EEC) correlate with SOH.

Despite the growing interest in utilizing EIS-based techniques for battery diagnostics, most of these studies focus on the analysis of individual battery cells. In real-world applications, however, it is often not possible to analyse only a single cell, as they are welded together within a battery module [13], making non-destructive disassembly unfeasible.

For this reason, the present work focuses on the potential of the application of the EIS method to entire battery modules, without requiring their disassembly, in order to obtain information about the SOH of the module. The aim of this study is to determine whether the conclusions presented in previous research are also applicable to entire battery modules. Specifically, it investigates whether the EEC parameters extracted from the measured EIS curve correlate with SOH-related parameters.

During the research, four battery modules in a 2P3S configuration were tested under cyclic aging, where the modules were subjected to full charge-discharge cycles starting at SOH 100% down to SOH 60%. Periodic RPT were performed throughout the aging process, during which both the capacity and EIS of the modules were tested. The results of this study demonstrate that:

- The EEC parameters R_s , R_1 and N_1 , obtained by fitting the measured EIS curve to the EEC, show a strong correlation with the SOH of the battery module, making them highly suitable for SOH analysis of battery modules.
- The parameters Q_1 and Q_2 exhibit a moderate correlation with the SOH trend observed throughout the lifetime of the module, indicating their potential as complementary indicators in methods based on R_s , R_1 and N_1
- The parameters N_2 and R_2 show only a weak correlation with SOH and therefore do not appear to be suitable for further SOH analysis based on EIS.

The main outcome of this work is the experimentally supported conclusion that the parameters R_s , R_1 and N_1 strongly correlate with the SOH of battery modules. Given the growing number of electric vehicles and the increasing importance of finding solutions for managing end-of-life (EOL) batteries [14], this finding may serve as a foundation for the development of methods aimed at sorting battery modules at the transition point between first-life and second-life applications.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Experimental Ageing of Battery Modules

All experimental work was carried out at the Laboratory for Energy Storage and Microgrids at UPNA, Spain. During the experiment, four identical battery modules in a 2P3S configuration were subjected to cyclic aging at room temperature. The modules are labeled sequentially from one to four and are subsequently referenced in the text as M1 to M4. The modules were composed of EX-L10 lithium iron phosphate (LFP) cells. The nominal capacity of each battery module was $C_n = 20$ Ah, and the nominal voltage was $U_n = 9.6$ V. Operating voltage range was 7.5 – 10.8 V.

Cyclic aging was performed using a Neware CE-6008n-30V30A-HF tester, and EIS was conducted using a frequency response analyzer, model PSM3750, manufactured by Newtons4th Ltd.

Fig.1. Tested battery module in laboratory during experiment.

B. Cyclic Ageing and Reference Performance Testing

All battery modules were aged using the same cycling profile. The primary reason was to obtain statistically significant insights into the degradation processes occurring within the module and how these are reflected in the EIS curves. The batteries were cycled between 0% and 100% state of charge (SOC). Charging was performed in constant current–constant voltage (CC-CV) mode with a charging current of 1C, i.e., 20 A, cut-off voltage $U_{\text{cut-off}} = 10.8$ V and a cut-off current set to $I_{\text{cut-off}} = 2$ A, corresponding to 10% of the charging current. Discharging was conducted in constant current mode using the same current as during charging, i.e., 20 A. The cut-off voltage was set to $U_{\text{min}} = 7.5$ V.

If the maximum allowable voltage for a single cell was reached before the entire module was fully charged or discharged, the charging or discharging process was terminated prematurely.

To obtain detailed information on the ongoing battery degradation, RPT was performed periodically every 100 to 200 cycles. The RPT procedure consisted of capacity measurement and EIS measurement. The specific procedure is outlined below:

1. Discharge the module to SOC = 0%, C-rate = 1C.
2. Charge the module in CC-CV mode to SOC = 100%, C-rate = 1C, cut-off voltage 10.8 V, cut-off current C/10.
3. Discharge the module in CC mode to SOC = 0%, C-rate = 1C, cut-off voltage 7.5 V.
4. Charge the module to SOC = 50%.
5. Rest for 1 hour.
6. Measure the EIS of the battery module (frequency range: 3 kHz – 0.1 Hz).

The module capacity was determined based on the discharged capacity at step 3.

C. Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy

EIS is based on the application of a small AC signal over a wide frequency range and the measurement of the resulting response. The impedance of the battery is then calculated using Fast Fourier Transform from the difference between the excited and sensed signals across all measured frequencies [7]. The results are typically visualized as a Nyquist diagram,

where the EIS curve is plotted with the imaginary part of the impedance on the y-axis and the real part on the x-axis [9]. Each part of the EIS curve represents a different electrochemical process occurring inside the cell, which enables separate analysis of the impact of degradation on individual electrochemical phenomena [15].

Fig. 2 illustrates which sections of the curve correspond to specific electrochemical processes inspired by [16].

Fig. 2. EIS curve of LFP battery module measured during experiment.

As the battery ages, the shape and position of the EIS curve changes [17]. The possible approach to quantifying these changes is to fit the EIS curve to an EEC and subsequently evaluate the values of the individual circuit parameters and their evolution during degradation. The equivalent circuit selected for fitting the measured EIS curve is shown in Fig. 3. Parameters R_s and L_s are related to the ohmic and inductive region, parameters R_1 and constant phase element (CPE) CPE_1 are related to SEI and charge-transfer region, and R_2 and CPE_2 correspond to diffusion region. CPE consist of two parameters Q and N [9]. Since the L_s parameter does not provide any specific information related to battery degradation, it is not included in the following analysis [9].

Fig. 3. EEC used for fitting EIS curves of LFP battery cells.

D. Correlation Between EEC Parameters and SOH

Since the objective of this study is to determine whether EIS measurement and EEC parameters can be used for SOH analysis of battery modules, the results will be evaluated by calculating the correlation between the SOH curves of the battery modules and the individual EEC parameters. The correlation will be assessed using the correlation coefficient, which is defined as:

$$r = \frac{\sum(x_i - \bar{x})(y_i - \bar{y})}{\sqrt{\sum(x_i - \bar{x})^2 \sum(y_i - \bar{y})^2}}, \quad (2)$$

where x_i and y_i are data points, \bar{x} is the mean of x values and \bar{y} is the mean of y values [18].

III. RESULTS

A. Capacity Testing and SOH

The results of the capacity testing, shown in Fig. 4, indicate that although all modules were initially assembled from new battery cells, this does not guarantee a uniform operational lifetime. This finding emphasizes the need for

reliable diagnostic methodologies for battery modules. The difference in reaching EOL, which is defined as a decrease in capacity to 80% of the nominal value [2]. Between the M1 and M2 the difference in the number of cycles before reaching EOL is 459 cycles, as illustrated in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. SOH of battery modules during ageing related to full cycles.

B. EIS Measurement and EEC Fitting

The equivalent circuit parameters were obtained by fitting the measured EIS curves to the EEC shown in Fig. 3. The fitting was performed using the Zfit function in MATLAB [19]. In all cases, the root mean square error of the fit did not exceed 2%, with an average fitting error of 0.85%. The evolution of the parameters with respect to the number of cycles for the tested modules is presented in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5. Fitted EEC parameters for different tested modules.

While certain parameters shown in Fig. 5 exhibit a clear trend of change with an increasing number of cycles (e.g., R_s , R_1 , or Q_2), others show only minimal trends during ageing (e.g., R_2 , N_2). Therefore, it was necessary to quantify these changes, which is addressed in the following section.

C. Correlation Between EEC Parameters and SOH

According to equation (2), correlation coefficients were calculated for all EEC parameters and the corresponding SOH curves of each module. The results are presented in Table 1. In general, the closer the correlation coefficient is to one or minus one, the stronger the linear correlation between the two variables [18]. Conversely, values near zero indicate a very weak or non-existent correlation. This is visually represented in the table using colour shading. Darker colours correspond to stronger correlations. The last column of the table shows the average of the absolute values of the correlation coefficients for each EEC parameter within a given module.

TABLE I. CORRELATION COEFFICIENTS CALCULATED FROM SOH AND EEC PARAMETER OF THE MODULE.

	M1	M2	M3	M4	average
R_s	-0.96	-0.85	-0.83	-0.96	-0.90
R_1	-0.95	-0.8	-0.64	-0.94	-0.83
Q_1	0.7	0.32	0.34	0.66	0.51
N_1	0.73	0.86	0.76	0.57	0.73
R_2	0.27	-0.13	0.09	0.22	0.11
Q_2	0.85	0.64	0.49	0.83	0.70
N_2	-0.59	-0.3	0.11	-0.19	-0.24

A strong correlation (defined as a correlation coefficient greater than 0.7 or less than -0.7 [18]) was observed for the parameters R_s , R_1 , and N_1 . A moderate correlation, i.e., a coefficient in the range of 0.3 to 0.7 (and analogously for negative values), was found for the parameters Q_1 and Q_2 . In contrast, the parameters R_2 and N_2 exhibited correlation coefficients below 0.3 or above -0.3, indicating only a very weak correlation.

These findings suggest that if the goal is to analyse the SOH of battery modules based on EIS measurements, the most suitable are the parameters related to growth of SEI layer and ohmic inductance of the cell (R_s , R_1 , and N_1) potentially supplemented by the moderately correlated parameters Q_1 and Q_2 . For the practical implementation of methods based on these findings, the results indicate that, since the relevant parameters are derived from the part of the EIS curve measured at higher frequencies, it may not be necessary to perform measurements across the full frequency spectrum. Instead, the measurement can be limited to the corresponding range, up to a few hundred millihertz, which enables further reduction in the time required for testing.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This work presents an analysis of an EIS measurement and parameter fitting procedure for diagnosing the state of health of Li-ion batteries at the module level. The proposed approach represents a step forward in bridging the gap between cell-level SOH diagnostic methods and the practical diagnostic tools needed for real-world applications based on module-level measurements. The proposal is demonstrated by means

of the presented experimental work, consisting on the ageing of four battery modules composed of six LFP battery cells in a 2P3S configuration. At regular intervals, capacity and EIS measurements were performed to monitor the module aging.

The measured EIS curves were fitted to an EEC model, from which the values of the equivalent circuit parameters were obtained throughout the entire aging period. Subsequently, the correlation between the SOH curves and the time evolution of the fitted EEC parameters was investigated. Correlation was evaluated based on the calculation of correlation coefficients. The results of the study demonstrate that:

- The EEC parameters R_s and R_1 and N_1 , obtained, show a strong correlation with the SOH of the battery module, making them highly suitable for SOH analysis of battery modules. The average value of the correlation coefficient for the R_s parameter is even 0.9.
- The parameters Q_1 and Q_2 exhibit a moderate correlation with the SOH trend observed throughout the lifetime of the module, indicating their potential as complementary indicators in methods based on R_s , R_1 and N_1 .
- The parameters N_2 and R_2 show almost no correlation with SOH, and therefore, they are not appropriate for further SOH analysis based on EIS.

All in all, this study presents experimentally supported conclusions that the equivalent circuit parameters R_s , R_1 , and N_1 exhibit a strong correlation with the SOH of battery modules. These conclusions may serve as a suitable foundation for the development of methods, for example, for sorting battery modules at the transition point between first life and second life, which, through the use of EIS instead of conventional capacity testing, can offer significant time savings.

Future research may aim to validate these results across a broader range of module configurations, including modules with higher capacities and voltages, as well as under different ageing conditions.

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